

THE EFFECTS OF SOCIAL CAPITAL ELEMENTS ON JOB SATISFACTION AND MOTIVATION LEVELS OF TEACHERS

Mukadder Boydak Özan¹,

Tuncay Yavuz Özdemir²,

Zübeyde Yaraş³ⁱ

¹Professor, Fırat University, Elazığ, Turkey

²Assistant Professor, Fırat University, Elazığ, Turkey

³PhD Student Fırat University, Elazığ, Turkey

Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to examine the effects of social capital elements' on job satisfaction and motivation levels of teachers. The mixed method was used in the study. The quantitative data were analyzed through Correlation and Multiple Regression analyses. An interview form developed by the researchers was used for analyzing the qualitative data. According to the correlation analysis, there is a positive and high level of relationship between social capital and job motivation. According to the regression analysis results, the three sub dimensions of social capital are significant predictors of job motivation levels of teachers; the other finding suggests that only the communication-social interaction sub-dimension is a significant predictor of teachers' job satisfaction levels.

Keywords: capital, social capital, job satisfaction, motivation, teacher

1. Introduction

It is possible to talk about social capital in all social processes. The potential of human resources constitutes social capital in every group of the society, in short in every field, which requires collaboration (Ekinçi, 2012). In the broadest sense, social capital refers to the potential strength which can be activated at any time to achieve the common goals and the expectations of the society (Aydemir and Tecim, 2012). At the same time, social

ⁱ Correspondence: email zyaras@hotmail.com

capital in organizations comes to the forefront as a factor influencing job satisfaction and motivation of individuals and describes the network and communication between workers, realizing target goals and creating norms and mutual trust (Naghavi and Baharloo, 2012).

Social capital cannot exclude the individual from the society. According to this view, societies with social relationship networks will improve themselves and strong social networks are beneficial for both individual interests and also social interests (Anık, 2011: 90). When the main purpose of social capital is considered, social communication networks are regarded as valuable assets and communication networks constitute a basis for social commitment (Gultepe Ayalp, 2010).

Social capital is based on social virtues rather than on individuals and individual virtues. Social capital is related to gain values such as loyalty, honesty and reliability and to integrate them at the social dimension (Basak and Oztas, 2010). In short, social capital refers to body of human resources which is based on mutual trust and in which the members of institutionalized or half-institutionalized organizations are attached to each other with strong ties (Bourdieu, 1986, Putnam, 1995). Trust and collaboration based on human relations constitute the fundamental principle of social capital (Ekinci, 2012). As a social being, humans continue their lives by socially interacting with people like their family and friends in every setting they function such as their workplace, home and school. By taking into consideration social trust, individuals sustain their social relationships through the norms and values created by either themselves or by the society and their close environment (Gunduz, 2011). Social capital depends on the level of trust that rests within a society and is regarded as the most important factor in enabling societies to develop both financially and morally (San, 2007). In social capital, reliability is considered as the most crucial element and is defined as “social binder” in organizations. Trust binds people together and promotes the feeling of cooperation (Puusa and Tolvanen, 2006). Coleman states that social capital has a function of facilitating productive activities. With this respect, a society, in which trust and reliance is present, will have the capacity to achieve more than a similar society which lacks these values (Wallace and Wolf, 2004).

It is stated that the “having strong social networks within an organization” element of social capital increases job satisfaction and that job satisfaction and communication affect each other in the same direction (Karcioğlu, Timuroğlu and Çınar, 2009; Savcı and Aysan, 2016; Eroğlu, 2011). While social networks and connections were considered as metaphors, the considerable improvements in communication technologies have led to the perception that communicating with many people through the internet offers the individual a prestige. Participation in social

networks through the internet is increasing considerably and thus, participation in social networks has functioned in every period as a crucial social capital production element (Babacan, 2012: 89; Colak, Altinkurt and Yılmaz, 2014).

Relationships based on trust, which constitute the foundation of social capital, are considered as strong predictors of job satisfaction in organizations (Ozdemir, 2008; Oguz and Ataseven, 2016). Elements of social capital play an important role in realizing the goals of organizations. Thus, in order to achieve the goals at desired levels in educational organizations, which consider humans as they basis, social capital elements should be powerful. In such institutions, motivations will individually or collectively be at high levels, teachers' job satisfactions will be high and organizational achievement will be positively affected.

Working in schools with a high level of social capital is expected to increase teachers' motivation and job satisfaction levels. Teachers with high level of commitment and motivation are expected to have higher levels of job satisfaction and thus, the schools they work in will better achieve their goals. With this respect, quantitative and qualitative research methods were used together in this study to strengthen social capital elements in educational organizations and determine their effects on job satisfaction and motivation levels of teachers.

The following questions were asked for the quantitative dimension of the study.

1. In educational institutions, is there a relationship between social capital elements in job satisfaction and motivation?
2. In educational institutions, are social capital elements a predictor of teachers' job satisfaction perceptions?
3. In educational institutions, are social capital elements a predictor of teachers' motivational perceptions?

With regards to the study's qualitative dimension, the effect of social capital on teacher job satisfaction and motivation levels concerning reliability, commitment, sense of belonging, norms and values, communication networks and participation in making decisions was analyzed.

2. Research Method

Information about the study model, the population and sample of the study, data collection instrument, data collection and data analysis are given in this section.

2.1 Study Model

This study is a mixed method research conducted by implementing qualitative and quantitative research methods together. A method variation was carried out in the

study by using the quantitative and qualitative data together. Variation is a practice which aims at enriching the methods by using two or more methods at the same time which support each other or are integrated with each other (Buyukozturk, Kılıc Cakmak, Akgun, Karadeniz and Demirel, 2011). In addition, Yıldırım ve Simsek (2011) define method variation as using more than one research method at the same time to answer the same research question. Reliability and validity of a study increases when quantitative and qualitative data are used to support each other (Creswell, 2003).

2.2 Study Group

The “simple random sampling method” was used in determining the study group. According to this method, each unit within the population has the equal and independent chance of being selected in the sample. In other words, each individual has the equal the chance of being selected and neither participant affects the other individuals’ possibility of being selected (Buyukozturk and et al. 2011).

For the quantitative dimension, data was collected from 280 teachers working in Elazığ central district during the 2013-2014 academic years. When the data was analyzed, 28 of the data were incomplete or incorrect; therefore 252 scales were regarded as valid. Demographic information about the teachers participating in the study are given on Table 1:

Table 1: Demographic information about the teachers participating in the study

Branch		Gender		Age (Ave)		Seniority (Ave)			
Class		Other		Female		Male			
n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%		
83	32.9	169	67.1	136	54	116	46	38.1	14.3

61 teachers working in the same city constituted the study group of the qualitative dimension. Teachers in the study group were selected through the random sampling method.

2.3 Assessment Instruments

Three scales were used in the study as the data collection instrument. Information about these scales are given below:

A. Social Capital Scale: This scale, developed by Ekinçi (2008), consists of five point Likert type degreed items. Five options were given for each question to determine the frequency of the behaviors. These were degreed as “never”, “rarely”, “sometimes”, “often” and “always” (1-5). The scale consists of five sub-dimension and 67 items,

however, the short form consisting of 54 items was used in the study by the researcher. In the study conducted by Ekinçi (2008); the Cronbach Alpha internal consistency coefficient for the whole scale was .967 and the reliability coefficients of the five sub-dimensions were calculated separately. The Cronbach Alpha coefficient for the organizational commitment sub-scale was .875, .856 for the communication-social interaction sub-dimension, .906 for the collaboration sub-dimension, .912 for the reliability sub-dimension and .912 for the tolerance for differences and sharing norms sub-dimension. The Cronbach Alpha coefficient for the whole scale in this study was .97, .892 for the organizational commitment sub-scale, .896 for the communication-social interaction sub-dimension, .927 for the collaboration sub-dimension, .931 for the reliability sub-dimension and .939 for the tolerance for differences and sharing norms sub-dimension. These values indicate that the scale has internal consistency.

B. Job Motivation Scale: This scale, adapted by Tanrıverdi (2007), consists of five point Likert type degreed items. Five options were given for each question to determine the frequency of the behaviors. These were degreed as “I’m totally dissatisfied”, “I’m dissatisfied”, “I’m not sure”, “I’m satisfied” and “I am totally satisfied” (1-5). The scale consists of 18 items however; the short form consisting of 14 items was used in this study by the researcher. While the Cronbach Alpha internal consistency coefficient for the whole scale in the study conducted by Tanrıverdi (2007) was .903, in this study the Cronbach Alpha internal consistency coefficient was .889.

C. Job Satisfaction Scale: This scale, developed by Şahin (1999), consists of items determined with three degrees namely as “yes”, “somewhat” and “no”. The scale consists of six sub-dimensions and 42 items. The short form consisting of 23 items was used in the study by the researcher. While the Cronbach Alpha internal consistency coefficient for the whole scale was .903, it was .823 in this study.

2.4 Data Analysis

The data collected through the quantitative data analysis were transcribed into special software and analyzed through it. The percentage and frequency techniques were used to express the demographic characteristics of the participants.

A correlation analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between social capital elements job satisfaction and motivation. The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient Technique was used in the correlation analysis. In interpreting the correlation coefficients, values between 1.00-0.70 indicated a high; values between 0.70-0.30 indicated a moderate; values between 0.30-0.00 indicated a low level of relationship (Buyukozturk and et al. 2011). A multiple regression analysis was conducted to determine the effects of social capital elements on the job satisfaction and

motivation levels of teachers. The stepwise regression method was used in the Multiple Regression Analysis. This method was used to analyze effects of the independent variables (demographic variables and social capital elements) on the dependent variables (job satisfaction and job motivation) separately.

The qualitative data were analyzed through the content analysis method. Similar data and certain terms and contexts are gathered together in the content analysis method. The purpose of content analyses is to gather terms and relationships that explain the collected data (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2011). The reliability of the study was calculated through the formula developed by (Miles and Huberman, 1994); Percentage of Agreement (P) = Agreement (Na) / Agreement (Na) + Disagreement (Nd) X 100. In qualitative studies, 90% and above fit values between the expert and researcher evaluations are considered as reliable. The researchers only placed 23 items in a different category. The reliability of the data was; P = 439/ (439 + 23) X 100 = 95%. Thus, the internal consistency of the scale was provided. In order to provide external validity, the study sample was selected in order to allow a generalization.

3. Findings

The Relationship between Social Capital and Job Motivation and Job Satisfaction Level Table 2 displays the correlation matrix which indicates the relationship between teacher perceptions on social capital and the levels of job satisfaction and job motivation:

Table 2: The correlation matrix displaying the relationship between demographic variables, social capital, job motivation and job satisfaction

	A	1	2	3	4	5	B	C	D	E
A. Social Capital	1	.77**	.88**	.89**	.91**	.78**	.63**	-.23**	0	0.08
1. Organizational Commitment	.77**	1	.61**	.58**	.56**	.51**	.51**	-.17**	0.09	0.06
2. Communication - Social Interaction	.88**	.61*	1	.77**	.76**	.55**	.52**	-.24**	-0.01	0.1
3. Collaboration - Social Network and Participation	.89**	.58**	.77**	1	.82**	.67**	.51**	-.24**	-0.02	0.1
4. Reliability	.91**	.56**	.76**	.82**	1	.71**	.56**	-.19**	-0.33	0.1
5. Tolerance for Differences and Sharing Norms	.78**	.51**	.55**	.67**	.71**	1	.61**	-0.12	-0.03	-0.03
B. Job Motivation	.63**	.51**	.52**	.51**	.56**	.61**	1	-0.11	-0.02	0.05
C. Job Satisfaction	-.23**	-.17**	.24**	-.24**	-.19**	-.12**	-0.11	1	0.02	0
D. Gender	0	0.09	-0.01	-0.02	-0.03	-0.03	-0.02	0.02	1	.16**
E. Branch	0.08	0.06	0.1	0.1	0.1	-0.03	0.05	0	.16**	1

* p<.05; N= 252; **p<.01; N= 252

According to Table 2, there is a statistically significant relationship between social capital and job motivation ($r = .063$; $p < .01$). It is evident that when the frequency of displaying behaviors related to social capital increase, job satisfaction levels of teachers also increase. Working in schools with high social capital levels will accordingly have positive effects in the teachers' interest' and desires to succeed. It is evident in study results that there is a common change in the increase in social capital levels in schools and teachers' interests towards their profession. A reverse and low level of relationship is observed between social capital and job satisfaction ($r = -.23$; $p < .01$). Teachers with low job satisfaction levels were observed to tend to perceive behaviors concerning the state of social capital at lower levels.

While there were no significant relationships between the gender variable and the social capital level ($r = .00$; $p > .05$), job motivation ($r = -.02$; $p > .05$) and job satisfaction ($r = .02$; $p > .05$) dimensions, there were also no significant relationships between the branch variable and the social capital level ($r = .08$; $p > .05$), job motivation ($r = .05$; $p > .05$) and job satisfaction ($r = .00$; $p > .05$) dimensions.

Thus, it can be said that there is a low level relationship between the demographic variables of the study and the opinions concerning social capital, job motivation and job satisfaction. However, a positive and high level relationship was detected between social capital and job motivation. In other words, the increase in social capital levels of schools enables teachers to be more willing in the profession and increases their job motivation.

3.1 The Effects of Social Capital Elements on Job Motivation

Results of the regression analysis conducted to determine the effects of social capital elements on job motivation are given on Table 3.

Table 3: The effects of social capital elements on job motivation

Variables	B	R	ΔR^2	β	t	p
Organizational Commitment	.199	.655	.428	.191	3.502	.003*
Communication- Social Interaction	.204	.668	.447	.175	2.089	.038*
Tolerance for Differences and Sharing Norms	.401	.612	.374	.402	5.690	.000
Dependent Variable: Job Motivation						
$R^2 = .450$ $F = 40,270$ $Sd = 1;246$ $p = 0.000$						

According to Table 3, the gender and branch variables among the independent variables and the collaboration and reliability variables of social capital were excluded from the regression model because they did not significantly contribute to the model. However, the three sub-dimensions of social capital (organizational commitment,

communication-social interaction, tolerance to differences and sharing norms) were observed to contribute significantly to the model and to explain 45% of the total variance concerning teachers' job motivation levels. When the regression coefficients are considered, it is evident that the communication-social interaction sub-dimension of the social capital scale explains almost 45% of total variance and thus is the best predictor. The organizational commitment and tolerance to differences and sharing norms sub-dimensions follow this sub-dimension by explaining 43% and 37% of the variance respectively.

It is remarkable finding that the communication-social interaction sub-dimension of the social capital scale is the best predictor of teachers' job motivation levels (44.7%). The fact that teachers continued to communicate with their colleagues even after their work hours might have supported them to generate positive perceptions towards their institutions and positively affected their motivation levels.

The organizational commitment and tolerance to differences and sharing norms sub-dimensions of the social capital scale were observed to be significant predictors of teacher perceptions concerning their job motivations. Thus, it can be stated that working in schools where democratic attitudes take place and where teachers feel themselves like a member of the institution increases motivation.

3.2. The Effects of Social Capital Elements on Job Satisfaction

Table 4 displays the results of the multiple regression analysis conducted to determine the effects of social capital elements on job satisfaction.

Table 4: The effects of social capital elements on job satisfaction

Variables	B	R	ΔR^2	β	t	p
Communication-Social Interaction	-.090	.249	.062	-.249	-4.072	.000*
Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction						
$R^2 = .062$ $F= 16,584$ $Sd= 1,250$ $p= 0.000$						

According to Table 4, the gender and branch variables among the independent variables and the organizational commitment, collaboration, reliability and tolerance to differences and sharing norms variables of social capital were excluded from the regression model because they did not significantly contribute to the model. The communication-social interaction sub-dimension of the social capital scale was observed to be a significant predictor of teachers' perceptions concerning their job satisfaction levels and it explained 6% of the total variance. It can be concluded that

having no communication barriers among teachers and between teacher-administrators will have a positive effect the job satisfaction levels of teachers.

With regards to the study's qualitative dimension, semi-structured interview forms were conducted to examine the effects of the reliability, commitment, sense of belonging, norms and values, communication networks and participation in decision making dimensions of social capital on teachers' job satisfaction and motivation levels. The data collected from these forms were examined through a content analysis. Findings are given below under the titles:

3.3 The Effects of Reliability on Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Motivation Levels

The themes, sub-themes and frequency values collected from teacher responses to the question "Does reliability towards your institution, administrators and colleagues have any effects on your job satisfaction and motivation?" are given on Figure 1.

Figure 1: The effects of reliability on job satisfaction and motivation

According to Figure 1; teacher opinions which stated that reliability has a positive effect on teacher job satisfaction and motivation levels were more frequent (f=70). Teachers who stated that it has a positive effect listed the grounds as enabling persistency (f=8), increasing productivity (f=9), strengthening commitment (f=12), increasing achievement (f=19), promoting school culture (f=2) and generating school climate (f=20). In addition, there was also a teacher opinion (f=1) expressing that reliability has no effect on job satisfaction. The following is an example of the opinions.

Example opinions

“Reliability has an effect on job satisfaction and motivation. My motivation is high when my administrator is fair and gives me confidence. Rather than leaving the school when my lessons finish, I would stay longer and work to achieve our organization’s goals.” (P17)

“A positive climate will occur in the institution when the administrator relies on the workers. Work gets more interesting and a strong organizational culture emerges. My motivation and job satisfaction will be high. (P20)”

“This effect is at higher levels in some organizations. Both job satisfaction and job motivation will be negatively affected when there is no trust within the setting. As an administrator and a leader, I think that the primary duty is to optimize the sense of reliability between the organization, administrator and workers within the institution. (P21)”

3.4 The Effects of Commitment on Teachers’ Job Satisfaction and Motivation Levels

The themes, sub-themes and frequency values collected from teacher responses to the question “Does commitment towards your institution have any effects on your job satisfaction and motivation?” are given on Figure 2.

Figure 2: The effects of commitment on job satisfaction and motivation

According to Figure 2; teacher opinions which stated that commitment has a positive effect on teacher job satisfaction and motivation levels were more frequent (f=64). Teachers who stated that it has a positive effect listed the grounds as increasing achievement (f=6), increasing reliability (f=9), increasing job satisfaction (f=12), strengthening the sense of belonging (f=10), promoting a positive school climate (f=10) and promoting the sense of responsibility (f=17). However, there were also teacher opinions stating that commitment has a negative effect on job satisfaction (f=5). Teachers stated the reasons for these opinions as; commitment affecting school climate (f=3) and frequent appointments (f=2). The following is an example of the opinions.

Example opinions

“No, because: I prefer professionalism in my work place. Because I would carry out my duty with devotion regardless of the location, the setting is not important for me.” (P14)

“Yes because; I see myself as a member of a family. I am committed to my institution due to my colleagues and the distribution of responsibilities in my workplace.” (P24)

“No, because: I changed seven schools in eleven and a half years. (appointment, promotion etc.) Through normal processes, without being relegated. This prevents me from adhering to the school.” (P47)

“Yes because; I exist with this institution and I am here...” (P61).

3.5 The Effects of the Sense of Belonging on Teachers’ Job Satisfaction and Motivation Levels

The themes, sub-themes and frequency values collected from teacher responses to the question “Do you see yourself as a member of your institution?” are given on Figure 3.

Figure 3: The effects of the sense of belonging on job satisfaction and motivation

According to Figure 3; teacher opinions which stated that the sense of belonging has a positive effect on teacher job satisfaction and motivation levels were more frequent (f=61). Teachers who stated that it has a positive effect listed the grounds as; increasing the sense of belonging (f=21), loving the profession (f=6), promoting the sense of responsibility (f=9), behaving according to the goals (f=13), promoting a positive school climate (f=9), being valued (f=3) and creating a school culture (f=1). However, there were also teacher opinions stating that the sense of belonging has a negative effect on job satisfaction (f=7). Teachers stated the reasons for these opinions as; affecting the school climate (f=3) and frequent appointments (f=2). The following is an example of the opinions.

Example opinions

“Yes, because: I am a worker, a member of this institution. I am one of the individuals who will achieve the goals of the organization.” (P5)

“No, because: there is no strong school culture and the school climate fails to help us feel like a member of the institution.” (P7)

“Yes, because: when I participate in and support the practices and individual activities (project etc.) of the institution I feel myself comfortable and calm and have the desire to do something for the institution.” (P11)

3.6 The Effects of Norms and Values on Teachers’ Job Satisfaction and Motivation Levels

The themes, sub-themes and frequency values collected from teacher responses to the question “Does your colleagues’ and administrator’s concern for norms and values affect your job satisfaction and motivation levels?” are given on Figure 4.

Figure 4: The effects of norms and values on job satisfaction and motivation

According to Figure 4; teacher opinions which stated that the norms and values have a positive effect on teacher job satisfaction and motivation levels were more frequent (f=46). Teachers who stated that they have a positive effect listed the grounds as increasing reliability (f=6), enabling to participate in the decision making process (f=4), increasing achievement (f=10), promoting a positive school climate (f=26) and enabling persistency (f=2). However, there were also teacher opinions stating that norms and values have a negative effect on job satisfaction and motivation (f=5). Teachers stated the reasons for these opinions as; being insincere (f=1) and failing to achieve goals (f=4).

Example opinions

“Yes because: norms and values are of course important the climate and atmosphere of the organization. It improves unity and commitment.” (P2)

“No, because: image and prescriptivism comes to the forefront.” (P4)

“Yes, because: when administrators underline ethical norms, then the sense of belonging of the workers will increase. Their motivation will increase. Individuals will be satisfied with their jobs. Workers who are more devoted and meticulous distinguish themselves with administrators who care about ethical norms.” (p18)

“Yes, because: I feel more comfortable and happy when values are protected, when values are sustained and when people work by stating loyal to norms. This enables me to succeed.” (P31)

3.7 The Effects of Communication Networks on Teachers’ Job Satisfaction and Motivation Levels

The themes, sub-themes and frequency values collected from teacher responses to the question “Does your administrators collaborating and strengthening their communication networks (social networks) with their shareholders affect your job satisfaction and motivation levels?” are given on Figure 5:

Figure 5: The effects of communication networks on job satisfaction and motivation

According to Figure 5; teacher opinions which stated that social networks have a positive effect on teacher job satisfaction and motivation levels were more frequent (f=55). Teachers stating that it has a positive effect listed the grounds as; increasing commitment (f=24), collaboration (f=21), solving problems (f=2) and communication (f=8). The following is an example of the opinions.

Example opinions

“Yes, because: gaining the support of our shareholders will form the basis for our future practices. If we gain the support and opinions of our shareholders our achievements will increase.” (P8)

“Yes, because: my job satisfaction and motivation levels are highly related to collaboration and social networks. Social networks affect communication and commitment.” (P10)

“Yes, because: the existence of such networks in schools will affect motivation. For example, there are no social networks in our school but you can carry out information exchange through the SMS system.” (P11)

3.8 The Effects of Participation in Decision Making in the Management Process on Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Motivation Levels

The themes, sub-themes and frequency values collected from teacher responses to the question “Does actively participating in the decision making process in your institution affect your job satisfaction and motivation?” are given on Figure 6.

Figure 6: The effects of participation in decision making on job satisfaction and motivation

According to Figure 6; teacher opinions which stated that participating in decision making has a positive effect on teacher job satisfaction and motivation levels were more frequent (f=55). Teachers who stated that this has a positive effect listed the grounds as; commitment to work (f=11), achievement (f=12), reliability (f=3), democratic setting (f=3), value (f=17) and responsibility (f=9). The following is an example of the opinions.

Example opinions

“Yes, because: administrators who ask for workers’ opinions when making decisions gain credits. The worker will respect the decision he agreed to. He will follow his decision with devotion. His motivation and job satisfaction will increase. He will feel himself better.” (P18)

“Yes, because; participating in the decision making process will enable me to feel like a member of the institution. It increases my motivation.” (P44)

“Yes, because: decisions taken in the institution will be more effective, productive and applicable when they reflect everyone’s opinions. Motivation and job satisfaction will increase when the workers take part in the process.” (P45)

4. Conclusion

According to the quantitative findings of this study, which aimed at determining the effects of social capital elements on teachers’ job satisfaction and motivation levels through quantitative and qualitative methods; there is a positive and high level of relationship between social capital elements and job motivation and there is a reverse

and low level of relationship between social capital elements and job satisfaction. According to a study conducted by Cankaya and Canakçı (2011) to examine the relationship between social capital and motivation levels of teachers, there is a significant positive relationship between social capital and motivation. According to the analysis results, there are no significant relationships between the gender variable and the social capital level, job motivation and job satisfaction dimensions and also between the branch variable and the social capital level, job motivation and job satisfaction dimensions. When the literature is considered, the finding stating the relationship between social capital level and job satisfaction is opposite the results of the studies in the literature. Other studies in the literature state that there is a positive relationship between job satisfaction and social capital (Ozmen, Akuzum, Kocoglu, Tan ve Demirkol, 2014; Akuzum and Tan, 2014).

According to the regression analysis results, the three sub-dimensions of social capital (organizational commitment, communication-social interaction, tolerance for differences and sharing norms) are significant predictors of job motivation levels of teachers. It was also observed that the communication-social interaction sub-dimension of the social capital scale is the best predictor of teachers' job motivation levels and that the organizational commitment and tolerance to differences and sharing norms sub-dimensions followed it respectively. Bilgin and Kaynak (2008) state that the elements of social capital positively contributed to work achievement.

According to the findings of the regression analysis, only the communication-social interaction sub-dimension of the social capital scale is a significant predictor of teacher perceptions concerning their job satisfaction levels. However, according to a study conducted by (Ozmen, Akuzum, Kocoglu, Tan ve Demirkol, 2014; Akuzum and Tan, 2014), social capital is a crucial predictor of job satisfaction.

With regards to the study's qualitative dimension, teachers stated that the reliability, commitment, sense of belonging, sharing norms and values, communication networks and participating in the decision making process dimensions of social capital have positive effects on teachers' job satisfaction and motivation levels. Teachers stated that when they have confidence their motivation and satisfaction towards their jobs will increase because their productivity will increase, commitment will become stronger, achievements will increase, they will have a stronger school culture and enable a more positive school climate to emerge accordingly. Teachers, who are commitment to their work and feel like a member of the school, stated that their job satisfaction and motivation levels will increase as a positive school climate is created, as their reliability and achievements increase and as their responsibilities towards their jobs strengthen. Poyraz and Kama (2008) state that organizational commitment has a positive effect on

job satisfaction. One other finding stated by Poyraz ve Kama (2008) emphasizes that individuals with high job satisfaction have higher organizational commitment; however, individuals with low job satisfaction levels tend to display behaviors which can damage the organization. Karataş and Gules (2010) state that teachers' desire to work, in other words high level of job motivation, increases organizational commitment. According to a study conducted by Cekmecelioglu (2005), organizational climate is related to job satisfaction, commitment and job performance levels of workers.

Social capital is the accumulation of capitals which are created through various connections by the human resources within an organization. This accumulation consists of elements such as reliability, communication, norms and common values. Because human constitute the basis of communication, it also constitutes the foundation of social accumulation. With this respect, it should be taken into consideration that because it directly affects each element of social capital, organizational communication has a crucial role. It can be concluded that social capital elements will be stronger in organizations with strong communication and that increased social capital accumulation will positively contribute to job satisfaction and motivation levels of teachers.

With regards to all these findings, it can be stated that teacher commitment and desire to work will increase in schools with high level of social capital and that their job satisfaction levels will increase in accordance with their motivations.

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